

CHANGES IN THE POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS OF HISORIAN BREED SHEEP

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Annotation: *At different physiological stages of postnatal ontogeny of Hissar sheep, some histological parameters of the biceps were studied, and the growth rate of the absolute perimeter thickness of the muscle was increased from 3 days to 60 months. 51 times, and 2.6 times in inadequate animals; the absolute value of muscle perimeter thickness in sheep in both regions increased from 3 days to 60 months of postnatal ontogeny, and in the stages, after 18 months it was slightly thicker in animals with inadequate conditions than inadequate conditions; The absolute indicator of muscle endometrial thickness is a rapid increase in postnatal ontogeny from 3 days to 12 months, regardless of living conditions of sheep, and a significant increase in the next 18, 36, 60 months, and all studied postnatal development in young sheep with adequate conditions was lower than in inadequate conditions.*

Keywords: *Hisorian breed sheep, postnatal ontogeny, adequate conditions, inadequate conditions, forefoot, muscle, growth rate, absolute index, muscle perimysium, endomesia.*

Introduction

In addition to the fact that the histological characteristics of the fibers that make up muscle tissue depend on their anatomical and topographic location and the scale of movement, they are in many respects affected by the natural living conditions of organisms. At the same time, the morphological structure, the determination of the laws of the dynamics of the development of histological structures at different physiological stages of postnatal ontogeny is of great scientific and practical importance.

The dynamics of growth of skeletal muscle tissue in sheep during postnatal ontogeny were studied [3], its weight increased rapidly from the neonatal stage to 4 months, followed by its slowing down to 10 months. , And at 12 months, the relative index was observed to rise slightly again. The author connects this situation with the manifestation of sexual deformity.

All animals can be divided into three types according to the rate of formation in ontogenesis in older individuals, namely, fast, moderate, and slow formation [4]. It would be appropriate to discuss the rate of formation of animals at a young age in terms of the fact that dissimilation processes continue to take precedence over assimilation processes. However, such an assessment can only be performed under laboratory experimental conditions. According to the author, a relatively simple method is to determine the rate of formation of animals as they decrease in relative weight.

The growth and development of muscle tissue in large horned cattle have been studied from the fetal period to 15 months of development [1] determined to return to the state. According to the author, a decrease in the level of animal nutrition leads to an increase in the amount of water and a decrease in the amount of water in the muscle tissue, while the amount of protein and ash remains unchanged.

The extracellular cast consists of many components. Some of them are composed of structural proteins such as collagen, elastins, which form fibrillar and reticular structures. Adhesive proteins such as fibronectin, laminin, fibulin bind structural proteins on the cell surface with transmembrane proteins. The cast forms a three-dimensional carcass through which the cell interacts with the entire surface [6, 7, 9].

According to some authors, when the myogenesis of cells derived from embryonic, fetal, and perinatal tissues was analyzed, it was found that they were not involved in the formation of skeletal muscle in adult vertebrates [5, 8]. Skeletal muscles have great plastic properties, have an internal ability to regenerate at the expense of satellite cells, and they are normally always active after injury [10]. As the body ages, the proliferative capacity of the satellite cells decreases, reducing the chances of skeletal muscle regeneration [11]. In addition to the cellular mechanism of regeneration of damaged muscle fibers, there is also an intracellular mechanism due to biosynthetic activation in the simplest, and the formation of new muscle fibers associated with muscle tubes, the survival of which is preserved [2].

Method and materials of inspection. Research works in Adequate - Boysun district of Surkhandarya region, "Boysun Terakli" farm and inadequate - Sariosiyo district, "Surkhan Hisor Koylari" farm, Uzun district "D Ruzibadal Shahrukh" farms. sheep were carried on muscles affecting the proximal section joints of the front leg. For scientific studies, animals in the 3-day, 3, 6, 12, 18, 36, and 60-month stages of postnatal ontogeny had their forelegs biceps.

The shoulder was taken from a biceps muscle measuring 0.5 x 0.5 x 0.2 cm, fixed in neutral formalin, dehydrated in alcohol, concentrated in ether, and solidified in a block. The histological incision was performed at HM 304E Semi-automated microtome. The histological preparation was stained with hematoxylin and eosin and measured under a microscope MB 200 (lens 20x10 eyepiece and lens 40x10 eyepiece).

All numerical data obtained as a result of scientific research were mathematically processed by the method of Ye.K. Merkur'eva.

To determine the dynamics of change in muscle fiber diameter and area with age, the growth factor was determined using a formula developed by KBSvechin.

Mathematical-statistical analysis was performed in a computer's Microsoft Excel spreadsheet using Student and Fisher criteria.

The results obtained and its discussion. As a result of scientific research, the histological characteristics of the biceps muscle of sheep bred in different natural conditions are differentiated according to the anatomical and topographic condition at different physiological stages of postnatal ontogeny, the scope of its function, and the natural conditions of animals` changes were observed.

Absolute indicator of the thickness of the perimeter of the biceps muscle of the shoulder in sheep under adequate conditions is an increase from $12.18 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{m}$ to $13.6 \pm 0.22 \mu\text{m}$ from the first 3 days to 3 months of postnatal development or during this period coefficient increased by 1.11 times ($r < 0.02$), a slight acceleration of this process at 6 months ($17.08 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{m}$; $K = 1.25$; $r < 0.23$), insignificant change at 12 months ($19.32 \pm 0.24 \mu\text{m}$; $K = 1.13$) and a steady increase during the next stages of development, ie at 18

months - $23.2 \pm 0.53 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.2$). ; $r < 0.03$), at 36 months - $27.92 \pm 0.35 \mu\text{m}$, and at 60 months - $30.66 \pm 0.53 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.09$; $r < 0.02$) was recorded. It was observed that the rate of growth of this muscle from 2.5 days to 60 months of postnatal ontogeny reached 2.51 times.

The absolute value of the thickness of this muscle perimeter was $12.16 \pm 0.56 \mu\text{m}$ in 3 days of postnatal ontogeny of sheep of inadequate natural conditions, which increased rapidly from 3 to 6 months (respectively, $14.22 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$; $18.04 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{m}$, $K = 1.26$, $r < 0.02$), a slight slowing of this process at 12 months (20.14 ± 0.2 ; $K = 1.11$) and subsequent There was a slight acceleration up to 60 months. That is, this muscle mass at 25 months was $25.04 \pm 0.41 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.24$; $r < 0.02$), and at 36 months it was $29.06 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1$). , 16), at 60 months $31.72 \pm 0.37 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.09$; $r < 0.02$), and from 3 days to 60 months of postnatal development, its growth rate was found to be 2.6 times.

Although the absolute thickness of the perimeter of the biceps is two to three to 60 months of postnatal ontogenesis in Hisorian sheep, especially in the 18 months of age, it is slightly thicker than inadequate animals were noted to be.

The absolute value of the thickness of the endometrial muscle of the shoulder increases slightly from the first 3 days to 12 months of postnatal development of ewes inadequate natural conditions, if this value is $0.97 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{m}$ in 3 days. Up to $1.33 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.37$) at 3 months, up to $3.68 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 2.76$; $p < 0.03$) at 6 months, 9 at 12 months, an increase of $54 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 2.59$; $r < 0.02$) was observed. In the later stages of postnatal ontogeny in animals, this morphometric size of the muscle increased almost steadily, ie at 18 months - to $9.7 \pm 0.18 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.01$; $r < 0.02$), 36 at $11.02 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.13$; $r < 0.03$) per month, at $12.64 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.14$; $r < 0.03$) at 60 months was noted. It was found that the growth rate of the absolute endometrial thickness of this muscle increased 13.02 times from the 3rd day to the 60th month of sheep postnatal development.

Up to 12 months of postnatal ontogenesis of sheep of inadequate natural conditions, there was a rapid thickening of the endometrium of the biceps, which is $0.98 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{m}$ at 3 days, 1.35 ± 0 at 3 months. $04 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.38$; $r < 0.04$), at 6 months - $4.44 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 3.28$; $p < 0.03$), at 12 months - $10.16 \pm 0.13 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 2.28$; $r < 0.02$). This muscle mass increases without significant changes at the age of 12 months, ie at 18 months - to $10.58 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.04$; $r < 0.01$), at 36 months - $11.28 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.06$), at 60 months - $13.96 \pm 0.26 \mu\text{m}$ ($K = 1.23$; $r < 0.02$), from 3 days of study of postnatal development It was noted that in the period up to 60 months, its growth rate reached 14.23 times.

Thus, the absolute indicator of the thickness of the endometrial muscle of the shoulder is a slight increase from the first days of postnatal ontogenesis to 12 months, regardless of the living conditions of sheep of the breed, and rises insignificantly in the following 18, 36, 60 months. Progression and postnatal development were observed to be lower in sheep under adequate conditions than in inadequate conditions at all studied ages.

Conclusions:

- The coefficient of growth of the absolute thickness of the perimeter of the biceps muscle from the first three days to 60 months of study of postnatal ontogeny was found to

be 2.51 times in sheep with adequate conditions and 2.6 times in animals with inadequate conditions;

- Although the absolute value of the thickness of the perimeter of the two-headed muscle of the shoulder increases from 3 days to 60 months of postnatal ontogeny in sheep of both breeds in both regions, especially in the stages after 18 months it is slightly thicker than in animals with inadequate conditions.

- An absolute indicator of the thickness of the biceps muscular endomezia is a rapid increase in postnatal ontogeny from 3 days to 12 months, regardless of living conditions in sheep, with a significant increase in the next 18, 36, 60 months and postnatal development in all studied ages, so sheep inadequate conditions were found to be lower than those in inadequate conditions.

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